

TRADITIONAL
SOUTH ASIAN
MEDICINE

8/2008

REICHERT

Some Neglected Aspects of Āyurveda
or
The Illusion of a Consistent Theory
II: The Suśrutasaṃhitā

GERRIT JAN MEULENBELD

The first part of this investigation¹ dealt with the relationship between *agni*² and *pitta* in the *Carakasamhitā* and, to a minor extent, the *Bhelasamhitā*. The conclusion reached was that *agni* is often different from *pitta*; as a separate agent, it is able to corrupt other bodily constituents and to cause disorders, while it is also a constituent liable to corruption by the *doṣas*. The *Carakasamhitā* thus shows traces of a not yet completed elaboration of the *tridoṣa* doctrine. The commentators strive to make these vestiges subservient to the prevailing classical theory which makes the *doṣas* into the only truly corrupting entities.

The relationship between *agni* and *pitta* is explicitly discussed in a prose passage of the *vraṇaprasna* chapter of the *Sūtrasthāna* (21,9). This well-known chapter is about the *doṣas*, blood, and the *kriyākāla*.³

The relevant passage appears abruptly and unexpectedly after a summarising verse,⁴ expressing that *kapha*, *pitta* and *vāta* sustain the body in the same way as moon (*soma*), sun (*sūrya*) and wind (*vāta*) sustain the world by their respective actions, consisting of emission (*visarga*), taking away (*ādāna*) and dispersion (*vikṣepa*). The parallelism of macro- and microcosm is at issue again here, as it was in the *vātakālākālīya* chapter of the *Carakasamhitā*.

¹ MEULENBELD *forthcoming*. At the time of going to press, this first part had not yet been published.

² The stem forms of the Sanskrit terms are not marked (i.e. *agni* instead of *agni-*), as this proved too cumbersome.

³ *Kriyākāla* means the proper time for particular therapeutic measures, dependent on the evolutive stage of a disease process.

⁴ *Suśrutasaṃhitā*, *Sūtrasthāna* 21,8:
visargādānavikṣepaiḥ somasūryāṇilā yathā
dhārayanti jagad dehaṃ kaphapittānilās tathā.

The subject matter of the prose passage that follows upon this verse surprises and catches the eye, in the same way as Marīci's words in the *vātakalākalīya* chapter. Again, one is tempted to consider the possibility of an interpolation.

The passage runs as follows:

*tatra jijñāsyam kiṃ pittavyatirekād anyo 'gnir āhosvit pittam evāgnir iti. atroc-
yate – na khalu pittavyatirekād anyo 'gnir upalabhyate, āgneyatvāt pitte dahanapacana-
nādiṣv abhipravartamāne 'gnivad upacāraḥ kriyate 'ntaragnir iti; kṣīṇe
hy agniguṇe tatsamānadravyopayogād ativrddhe śītakriyopayogād āgamāc ca
paśyāmo na khalu pittavyatirekād anyo 'gnir iti.*

With respect to this (*tatra*) one would like to know if there exists another fire (*agni*) than *pitta* or if *pitta* and fire are identical. The answer to this question is: certainly no other fire than *pitta* is known. The reason is that *pitta*, due to its fiery nature, and being engaged in (*abhipravartamāna*) burning (*dahana*), cooking (*pacana*) and the like, is, metaphorically speaking, like *agni* and therefore called the internal fire (*antaragni*). Verily, there is no other fire than *pitta*, as can be learnt from the use of similar substances when its fiery quality (*agniguṇa*) has diminished (*kṣīṇa*)⁵ and from the employment of cooling measures (*śītakriyā*) when it has increased too much; this can be learnt as well from trustworthy authorities (*āgama*).

The translation of this passage is not without some contentious points. The word *tatra*, with which it begins, has no referent in the preceding verse. The commentator Ḍalhaṇa notices this and feels obliged to list three different interpretations of *tatra*.⁶

This detail, small though it is, strengthens the thought that the passage may

⁵ The interpretation of *tatsamānadravya* is disputed. Ḍalhaṇa is of the opinion that substances similar to *agni* are meant; others, referred to by him, are convinced that *agniguṇa* denotes *uṣman* and that substances similar to *pitta* are intended.

⁶ (1) *Tatra* refers to the problem whether or not *pitta* and *agni* are identical; (2) *tatra* means *teṣu madhye* 'amongst these things'; (3) *tatra* points back to the *ādāna* of the preceding verse. A fourth group asks why the wish to know about the relationship between *pitta* and *agni* is relevant after mentioning *ādāna* in the set *visargādānavikṣepa*.

be an addition to a more original text. The second problem is the precise meaning of the expression *agnivad upacāraḥ kriyate*, which I rendered as '(pitta) is, metaphorically speaking, like agni'. SHARMA 1999 concurs with me in translating 'it is metaphorically identified with agni'.⁷ DUTT 1883 translated: 'it acts like fire', while SINGHAL/TRIPATHI/CHATURVEDI 1981 translate: 'it performs functions like agni'.⁸ These differences indicate that it is not completely clear whether *upacāra* is employed in a technical or in a more general sense. Ḍalhaṇa opts for the latter alternative, as some later commentators do; the resulting translation of *agnivad upacāraḥ kriyate* as 'it performs functions like those of agni' is permissible and does not give a wrong sense to the expression. In my opinion, however, most probably a metaphor comes into play, as attested by the suffix *-vat* in *agnivat* and because of the ambiguity of the train of thought.⁹

As to be expected, Cakrapāṇidatta and Ḍalhaṇa present elaborate comments on the passage.

Ḍalhaṇa begins with remarking that the passage demonstrates that the identity of *agni* and *pitta* can be proved by direct observation (*pratyakṣa*), inference (*anumāna*) and reliance on trustworthy authorities (*āgama*). He proceeds by introducing an imaginary opponent, who adduces proofs contradicting the identity. This evidence to the contrary consists of the existence of substances with effects on *pitta* that differ from those on *agni*¹⁰ and some passages from

⁷ As will be observed later, Śrīkaṇṭhadatta also supports this interpretation.

⁸ The English translation of BHISHAGRATNA 1963 has no clear equivalent of *upacāra*. Hārāṇacandra's nineteenth-century Sanskrit commentatry gives *vyavahāra* as the equivalent of *upacāra* (see BHATṬĀCĀRYYA et al. 1832), which means that it performs functions like those of *agni*. GHANEKAR 1952 also explains *upacāra* as *vyavahār* in his Hindi commentary.

⁹ The conclusion 'it is therefore called the internal fire' does not follow from the similarities between *pitta* and *agni*.

¹⁰ Examples adduced are: (1) ghee, which pacifies *pitta* while stimulating the fire (see *Suśrutasaṃhitā*, Sūtrasthāna 45,96); Cakrapāṇidatta gives an elaborate exposition on the actions of ghee in his comments on *Carakasamhitā*, Sūtrasthāna 13,13; (2) goat's milk, which has the same effects (see Sūtrasthāna 45,51cd-53ab); (3) fish, which make *pitta* increase without stimulating the fire (Sūtrasthāna 46,114^a only mentions that fresh water fish stimulate *pitta*, but is

the *Suśrutasamhitā* itself;¹¹ a quotation from an unmentioned source¹² completes the evidence to the contrary. I shall return to these objections later.

This opposition is superfluous in Ḍalhaṇa's eyes, for Suśruta, as well as others, acknowledge that in reality (*paramārthataḥ*) *pitta* and *agni* are distinct. A stanza from the Nidānasthāna (13,37), to be discussed later, is cited as evidence. Ḍalhaṇa goes on by intimating that he could provide more quotations in support, but that he abstains from doing so for fear of prolixity.¹³ He is apparently convinced that *agni* and *pitta* are not identical, but fails to specify of which type the difference may be. The most significant remarks occur at the end of his comments, where he declares that the statement of the *Suśrutasamhitā* about the absence of a difference between *agni* and *pitta* serves to show that *agni* can only be treated by means of therapeutic measures appropriate to *pitta*, because *pitta* is endowed with attributes such as taste (*rasa*), potency (*vīrya*), and the like, which *agni* does not possess;¹⁴ otherwise, disorders of *agni* would not be amenable to treatment.

The essence of Ḍalhaṇa's train of thought is that *agni* and *pitta* are actually distinct, but that this difference is neglected for practical purposes.

Completely absent from Ḍalhaṇa's deliberations is any reference to the verse (Sūtrasthāna 21,11) enumerating the qualities (*guṇa*) of *pitta* and closing the section on this *doṣa*, even though this stanza establishes beyond the shad-

silent about the effect on the fire; Sūtrasthāna 21,21 mentions fish in general as one of the items making *pitta* excited; I could not find a statement in the *Suśrutasamhitā* corroborating that of Ḍalhaṇa); (4) sleeping by day (Sūtrasthāna 21,23 mentions *divāsvapna* as one of the factors causing excitement of *kapha*, Śārīrasthāna} 4,38 regards sleeping by day as provoking all the *doṣas*).

¹¹ From Sūtrasthāna 35,24 and 15,41, and Nidānasthāna 13,37 on *palita*.

¹² *dravaṃ snigdham adhogam ca pittaṃ vahnir ato 'nyathā*.

¹³ He could have referred to Uttaratānta 39,16cd-19ab on the onset of fever, where it is said that the *doṣas* (one of which is *pitta*) make the (digestive) fire sluggish and expel the heat (*ūṣman*) from the seat of digestion, making it reach the surface of the body.

¹⁴ Substances (*dravya*) possess *guṇas*. Obviously, *agni* is not a substance; it is a *guṇa* of *pitta* according to Ḍalhaṇa ad Sūtrasthāna 21,9: *agner guṇo yasya tad agniguṇaṃ pittam*.

ow of a doubt clear-cut differences between *pitta* and *agni*.¹⁵

Cakrapāṇidatta's comments on the same passage bear witness to more theoretical subtlety and less concern for practice. This author does not pay attention to the word *tatra* and begins, tying in with what has been expressed in the preceding verse, by also making an objector appear, who argues: 'Well, but how does *pitta* perform, in the same way as the sun, the action called *ādāna*?' Cakrapāṇidatta replies to his opponent that the words of Suśruta aim at dispelling the doubt that there may be a difference between *agni* and *pitta*. Valid means of acquiring knowledge (*pramāṇa*) that could attest to such a difference are simply absent. Seeming (*avabhāsaka*) statements to the contrary, such as '*pitta* makes the fire *tikṣṇa*' (Sūtrasthāna 35,24), should not be taken literally. That is why Suśruta says '*pitta* is the same as fire on account of its fiery nature'. After establishing this point, the text of the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* makes use of inference in order to underpin its thesis (*pakṣa*) by referring to therapeutic measures which are recommended in disorders. The property (*guṇa*) of fire that has the ability to cook (*pācakatva*) as its characteristic, is its heat (*ūṣman*).¹⁶ When this heat has diminished, substances with properties similar to fire and similar to *pitta*¹⁷ can increase it, and conversely when the heat has increased. These effects are possible because *tejas* forms part (*avayavarūpa*) of *pitta* and acts by means of its fiery nature (*agnitva*). The substances mentioned cannot but possess this same *tejas* just because they are suitable to the purpose.

This having been settled, the thesis is also proved by having recourse to authority. Cakrapāṇidatta quotes as evidence in support Sūtrasthāna 26,20 and

¹⁵ The verse runs:

*pittaṃ tikṣṇaṃ dravaṃ pūti nīlaṃ pītaṃ tathaiva ca
uṣṇaṃ katurasaṃ caiva vidagdhaṃ cāmlam eva ca.*

It implies that substances with opposite qualities subdue *pitta* without impairing the fire.

¹⁶ Cakrapāṇidatta, who does not distinguish between *pitta* and *agni*, ascribes *guṇas* to *agni*, unlike Ḍalhaṇa; evidently, Cakrapāṇidatta is one of those, referred to in Ḍalhaṇa's commentary, who regard *ūṣman* as an *agniguṇa*.

¹⁷ This is remarkable in view of Ḍalhaṇa's statement that, depending on the interpretation of *agniguṇa*, either substances similar to fire or substances similar to *pitta* are intended.

Śārīrasthāna 4,18, two passages still to be dealt with, and a verse of Bhoja running: ‘The agent bringing about cooking (*paktimat*) is therefore *pitta*, which consists of *tejas*, which is the heat (*ūṣman*) of *pitta*.’¹⁸

Cakrapānidatta, so far apparently defending that *agni* and *pitta* are identical, begins to put his opinion in perspective in the subsequent part of his comments.

He opens this part by remarking: If there were actually no distinction between the two, there could not exist between them the same connection as that between cause and effect, as exemplified in the statement: ‘a *tīkṣṇa* fire is brought about by *pitta*’ (Sūtrasthāna 35,24). Absence of any distinction would also contradict other statements, such as found in a verse on *grahaṇīdoṣa* from the *Carakasamhitā* (Cikitsāsthāna 15,65) stating that *pitta* may, like hot water, extinguish the fire by flooding it.¹⁹ Two more passages from the *Suśrutasamhitā* would neither be acceptable in that case. The first of these quotations (Sūtrasthāna 45,96) lists the properties and actions of ghee, the second one (Sūtrasthāna 15,41) distinguishes a balanced state of the *doṣas* from a balanced state of the fire.

Though statements clearly demonstrating the absence of any difference do occur, such as ‘(foreign objects in the body) made of gold, silver, copper, brass, tin or lead, are, after a long stay there, dissolved by the heating action (*pratāpana*) of the *tejas* of *pitta*’ (Sūtrasthāna 26.20), yet words like those of Bhoja: ‘The heat (*ūṣman*) of *pitta* has the capacity to cook (*paktimat*)’, point to the fiery nature (*agnitva*) of *tejas* as being different from its substrate, *pitta*.

The inference (that *agni* and *pitta* are identical), based on the assertion that

¹⁸ The following sentence does not form part of the text in all the manuscripts: ‘This detailed exposition (*prapañca*) proves that *agni* is not distinct from *pitta*, since it exists in the form of the heat of *pitta*, and a difference between a property (*dharma*) and the substrate of that property (*dharmin*) does not exist.’ The use of the terms *dharma* and *dharmin* point to this sentence as being interpolated.

¹⁹ GAUTAM/UPĀDHYĀY/GAUTAM 2005 refer in their article to an author called Nirañjan Dev, who determined the *pāñcabhautika* composition of *pitta* as follows: *vāyu* and *ākāśa* 10%, *prthivī* 20%, *ap* 30%, *agni* 40%.

substances increasing *pitta* can also usefully be employed when the fire has grown weak, is not valid, since it is well known that some substances make the one increase while not stimulating but even hurting the other.²⁰

At this point Cakrapāṇidatta reaches his conclusion. He decides that Suśruta's words about the absence of a difference between *agni* and *pitta* mean that their only difference is the same as that between an attribute and the bearer of that attribute. A verse from the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* is cited with the aim of supporting this conclusion. This verse (Sūtrasthāna 35,27) runs: "The venerable (*bhagavat*) lord (*iśvara*), the abdominal fire (*jāṭharāgni*), who cooks the food and takes up (*ādadaṇa*) the tastes, can, on account of its subtlety (*saukṣmya*), not be perceived (*vi/vic*)". Subtleness is, according to Cakrapāṇidatta, a characteristic that cannot be applied to *pitta*, whereas it does suit heat (*uṣman*). In the expression 'the sixth *kalā* is that one called *pittadharā*' (Śārīrasthāna 4, 18), the word *pitta* is employed metaphorically²¹ and actually designates *agni*. The statement that substances increasing or decreasing *pitta* usually make *agni* increase or decrease as well, ought to be interpreted in a similar vein; it is to be understood in a metaphorical sense, because it does not distinguish between a property (*dharma*) and the bearer of that property (*dharmin*).

The acceptance of a distinction between the two, namely that *agni* exists in the form of the *tejas* of *pitta*, makes it intelligible that particular substances which increase the liquid part of *pitta*, but not the part consisting of *tejas*, may extinguish the fire by generating a kind of *pitta* that is *vyamla*, abnormally acid in taste.

Cakrapāṇidatta presents in this long discourse the same view as that found in his comments on Marīci's intervention in the *vātakalākalīya* chapter of the *Carakasamhitā*, where he is less prolix and indulges to a much lesser degree in theoretical considerations.

²⁰ In this Cakrapāṇidatta agrees with Dalhaṇa. Substances which are either *dīpana* or *pācana* or both simultaneously are distinguished in lists of drug actions in works like the *Śārīngadharasaṃhitā* (1,4,1-2ab). The *Suśrutasaṃhitā* itself also has groups of drugs which are either *pācana* or *dīpana* (Sūtrasthāna 38).

²¹ The term used is *aupacārikapittaśabdaprayoga*.

In short, he is convinced that the relation between *agni* and *pitta* is of the same kind as that between a property (*dharma*) and the bearer of that property (*dharmin*). Heat (*ūṣman* or *tejas*) is the *dharma* and *pitta* the *dharmin*. Cakra-pāṇidatta's conclusion implies that, wherever *pitta* is present, *agni* will be present too.

This conclusion is not free from blemishes. It is questionable whether *agni* is always dependent on *pitta* in the *Carakasamhitā* and *Suśrutasamhitā*. Minor flaws are that he does not distinguish between *ūṣman* and *tejas* (these are distinct in *Suśrutasamhitā*, Sūtrasthāna 15,4,2) and that he considers *agni* and *ūṣman* to be identical. He obviously aims, more so than Ḍalhaṇa, at the construction of a coherent theory, in which *agni* is not allowed to have a position that makes it, even partially, independent of the *doṣas*.

The prose passage that follows upon Sūtrasthāna 21,9 of the *Suśrutasamhitā* describes the five kinds of *pitta*, calling them not *pācakapitta* etc., but *pācakāgni* etc.

In this context an interesting verse from the *Suśrutasamhitā* which throws light on the relation between *pitta* and *ūṣman* has to be discussed. This verse was so conspicuous and problematic in the eyes of the commentators that it prompted them to expound and defend their views on *agni* and *pitta* in sometimes long discourses.

The pertinent verse is found in the chapter on *kṣudrarogas* of the Nidānasthāna (13,37) and forms also part of the chapter on the same subject of the *Mādhavanidāna* (55,32). Four comments are therefore available, those of Gayadāsa and Ḍalhaṇa on the *Suśrutasamhitā* and those of Śrīkaṇṭhadatta and Vācaspati on the *Mādhavanidāna*.²²

The verse runs:

*krodhaśokaśramakṛtaḥ śarīroṣmā śirogataḥ
pittaṃ ca keśān pacati palitaṃ tena jāyate*

The bodily heat (*śarīroṣman*), brought about by anger (*krodha*), grief (*śoka*), or

²² Hārāṇacandra's commentary on the Nidānasthāna of the *Suśrutasamhitā* is not available to me.

fatigue (*śrama*), and having moved to the head, cooks (*pacati*), together with *pitta*, the hair of the head; this generates greyness (*palita*).

It is important to see how the commentators reflect upon the juxtaposition of bodily heat and *pitta* in this stanza.

Gayadāsa, the oldest of the four, begins with remarking that, according to some, this is a case where two agents (*kartr̥*) are put together, namely bodily heat and *pitta*. That is not proper in his opinion. Obviously, Gayadāsa does not admit that two distinct types of agent produce, in collaboration, one and the same disorder. That makes him go on as follows: However, there does exist a difference, because pathological (*vaiḥṛta*) greyness is brought about by the heat of *pācakapitta*, and naturally occurring (*svābhāvika*) greyness by the *pitta* of one's constitution. In this interpretation, Gayadāsa identifies the bodily heat with the heat of *pācakapitta*. He proceeds by presenting an imaginary opponent who objects that, if things are thus, we have here a case (*prasaṅga*) of greyness that arises without a *doṣa*. The reply to this argument is: That is not correct, for greyness arises from a property (*dharma*) of *pitta*. This reasoning is evidently of the same type as that of Cakrapānidatta.

After a lacuna in the manuscript, Gayadāsa says: The situation is as follows: pathological greyness finds its origin in *pitta*, whereas natural greyness occurs in persons with a balanced constitution (*samadoṣaprakṛti*). For that reason it is not right to accept that two agents are mentioned in the verse; natural greyness is found in persons with a constitution dominated by *pitta*, and, as has repeatedly been explained, a constitution does not lead to pathological changes (*vikāra*), on account of the small amount of the *doṣa* (*alpadoṣatva*) in a particular constitution.²³

Gayadāsa thus subsumes bodily heat under the concept of *pitta* and refuses to recognise it as a separate agent. He solves the problem by distinguishing a pathological and a natural type of greyness of the hair. An imperfection in his reasoning is that he attributes natural greyness first to persons with a balanced constitution and later to those with a constitution dominated by *pitta*.

²³ Cf. *Suśrutasamhitā*, Śārīrasthāna 5,79.

Ḍalhaṇa also dislikes the two agents mentioned in the verse. He argues that bodily heat generates pathological greyness and *pitta* the naturally occurring type. Otherwise, since *pitta* and heat are the same, we would have here a case of useless repetition (*punaruktidoṣa*). He quotes the author of the commentary called *Pañjikā*, who says: ‘Bodily heat is the fire (*pāvaka*) and *pitta* is its substrate (*āsaya*); these two, having become one, perform the action of cooking.’ Ḍalhaṇa remarks that in this way the option of a pathological type of greyness, brought about by heat only, has been removed, for that would have been a disorder coming about without a *doṣa*.

Ḍalhaṇa’s line of thought thus resembles that of Gayadāsa, but without having recourse to the concept of constitution. Remarkable is that he here disowns his opinion, expressed on a former occasion, that *agni* and *pitta* are actually distinct.

Both Gayadāsa and Ḍalhaṇa do not want to acknowledge that two agents are found in the verse, keen as they are on dispelling any danger to the *tridoṣavāda*.

Śrīkaṇṭhadatta’s comments are very long and replete with quotations, which makes it expedient to present a condensed rendering.

He begins by saying: The bodily heat is the bodily fire; *pitta* is mentioned as having moved to the head too, in the same way as the bodily heat. An opponent may object that *pitta* is identical with fire because, at several instances, it is said to be endowed with the action of cooking (*pācakatva*); what may therefore be the reason that *pitta* and the fire are mentioned separately?

Śrīkaṇṭhadatta replies that this objection can be refuted. The internal fire (*antaragni*) and *pitta* are not identical to such an extent. This has been established more than once in authoritative statements. A reference to *Suśrutasaṃhitā*, Sūtrasthāna 15,41 (*samadoṣaḥ samāgnīś ca*), together with an unidentified quotation (*samaprakopau sarveṣāṃ doṣāṇām agnisamśrayau*), make Śrīkaṇṭhadatta declare that *agni* and *pitta* differ from each other, both being separately mentioned. He adds that the statement ‘*agni* becomes *tikṣṇa* through the action of *pitta*’ is an example of a contradiction in terms (*svātmani kriyāvirodhaḥ*). The difference between *agni* and *pitta* is, moreover, established by the

use of the term *upacāra* in the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* (Sūtrasthāna 21,9): a metaphor is not applicable in cases of identity. He also disagrees with the view that the identity of the two is established by the fact that substances with qualities similar to those of *pitta* make the fire increase; he adduces as a counter-example that, though substances with properties similar to those of *kapha* make semen increase, this does not prove at all that *kapha* and semen are identical. At the end of this part of his discourse, he mentions, as other commentators do, that ghee, which pacifies *pitta*, stimulates the fire; some new examples of the same phenomenon are provided: accumulation of *pitta* does not result in increase of the fire, and *peyā* (a thin kind of gruel) makes the fire increase without increasing *pitta*.²⁴

He proceeds by bringing forward that *pitta* is an aggregate (*samudāya*) of a fluid (*drava*) and a fiery part (*tejas*). The *tejas* part of *pitta* cannot, as fire does, reduce something to ashes (*aṅgārākāra*), since a whole differs from its component parts. The *tejas* part of *pitta* is the agent responsible for the cooking action.

Quotations serve to settle that assertions about the identity of *agni* and *pitta* should be interpreted metaphorically. A second question is then raised: Well, how can, if *pitta* makes the fire *tikṣṇa*, this same *pitta* extinguish (*praśamana*) the fire, as has been said in the *Carakasamhitā* (Cikitsāsthāna 15,65) with the words: ‘an abundant amount of *pitta* inundates the fire, in the same way as hot water’?

Śrīkaṇṭhadatta replies: When, by the intake of particular substances, *pitta* has increased, the fire becomes *tikṣṇa* due to the abundantly present *tejas* part of *pitta*; when, by the intake of other substances, *pitta*, accompanied by *kapha*, has increased, the fire is extinguished due to the prevalence of the liquid part of *pitta*.

Jatūkarṇa is quoted in support; this authority says: ‘The fire is, like a lamp, extinguished by excited *vāta*; it is extinguished by excited *pitta* as by hot water, and by excited *kapha* as by water.’ Śrīkaṇṭhadatta concludes that it is there-

²⁴ See *Suśrutasaṃhitā*, Sūtrasthāna 46,341cd-342ab.

fore proper to mention the fire separately.

Having reached this point, he is ready to interpret the verse of the *Mādhavanidāna* that occasioned this digression.

The fire, being part of *pitta*, is brought about by anger, for anger arises from excitement of *pitta*. The bodily heat has moved to the head by the dispersive action (*vikṣepaṇa*) of *vāta*, which originates from grief and fatigue. In this way *vāta* also plays its role; *pitta* is mentioned explicitly. The word *ca* in *pit-tam ca* adds *kapha*, which whitens the hair.

Thus interpreted, the verse expresses that greyness of the hair is caused by bodily heat, together with the three *doṣas*. This is in conformity with what the *Carakasamhitā* says (Cikitsāsthāna 26,132): '(Tejas), together with *vāta* and the other *doṣas*, having burnt the scalp, gives rise to baldness (*khalati*); when this burning is slight, greyness results or a reddish (*harit*) colour of the hair.'

Our author proceeds: These are the characteristics (*lakṣaṇa*) of all types of greyness that occur at an improper time (*akāla*), that is to say before the age in which it is naturally found; the type occurring in old age (*kāla*) is, though not mentioned, included (*upalakṣaṇa*). This type also originates from heat, together with the three *doṣas*; the latter are roused by the changes (*pariṇāma*) due to the stage of life (*vayas*); otherwise, it would be a missing item. Or, it may be that the type found in old age has been left unmentioned as a naturally occurring (*svābhāvika*) change.

Others, however, have expressed the opinion that bodily heat and *pitta* designate two agents, which boils down to an accumulation of agents with the same range of action (*viśaya*). Actually, the range of action is twofold. The bodily heat is at the origin of pathological (*vaikṛta*) greyness, while *pitta* is at the origin of natural greyness, found in persons with a constitution dominated by *pitta*. This agrees with what has been said: 'A *pittaprakṛti* goes together with premature wrinkles and greyness' (no source mentioned).

Thus, the natural greyness of old age has also *pitta* as its cause (*hetu*). The fact that greyness is brought about by heat is therefore not a case in which the *doṣas* are absent, because heat forms part of *pitta* as one of its attributes.

Śrikanṭhadatta's elaborate discussion is not clear in all respects. He strives

at incorporating everything found in his predecessors' works. On the one hand he expresses as his opinion that *ūṣman* is the fiery part of *pitta*, while, on the other, he gives some scope to the view that greyness of the hair arises from the bodily heat, together with the three *doṣas*.

The verse discussed appears, however, to recognise bodily heat as an agent distinct from *pitta*.

Vācaspati's short remarks do not provide new material. He regards *śarīroṣman* and *pitta* as identical. The view that *agni* and *pitta* are distinct is referred to, as well as the opinion that *palita* is brought about by the three *doṣas*.

Another verse from the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* may also establish that *agni* is distinct from the *doṣas*. As to be expected, it is therefore often quoted and made to mean that this is not the case. This verse (Sūtrasthāna 15,41) runs: 'A person is called healthy (*svastha*) when the *doṣas* and the fire are in a balanced state, when the functions (*kriyā*) of the *dhātus* and the *malas* are balanced, and when the *ātman*, the senses and *manas* are in a tranquil (*prasanna*) condition.'²⁵

Ḍalhaṇa's comments are conspicuous in being in conformity with what he expressed on an earlier occasion. First, he raises the question why the *ācārya*, i.e., Suśruta, refers to the *doṣas* and *agni* separately, since a balanced state of *agni* and of the other constituents mentioned is brought about by a balanced state of the *doṣas*. His answer is: It is not obligatory that a balanced state of *agni* and of other constituents of the body is dependent on the *doṣas*. The argument he adduces is that the *doṣas* and *agni* are distinct as to treatment, for ghee and goat's milk remove *pitta* and increase *agni*. In this way Ḍalhaṇa repeats his conviction that *agni* and *pitta* are not identical.

Cakrapāṇidatta also sticks to his opinion. He solves the difficulties raised by the verse by interpreting it as expressing that a person with balanced *doṣas* is characterised by a balanced fire and by balanced functions of the *dhātus* and *malas*. This reasoning implies that *agni* and *pitta* are identical.

A prose passage of the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* also gives the impression that *agni*

²⁵ *samadoṣaḥ samāgnis ca samadhātumalakriyaḥ
prasannātmendriyamanāḥ svasthā ity abhidhīyate.*

and the *doṣas* are distinct. This passage (from Sūtrasthāna 35,24) says: ‘*Agni* is the agent that cooks the food (*annasya pācakah*). ... When subject to a disorder (*vikriyām āpannaḥ*) it is of three types: ... [it becomes] *tikṣṇa* by *pitta*.’²⁶ This passage is well known to the commentators, who quote it when discussing on the status of *agni*, but neither Cakrapāṇidatta nor Ḍalhaṇa makes any remark on this topic in their comments on this occasion.

The *Suśrutasaṃhitā* contains, moreover, a verse that may not only confirm that *agni* is distinct from the *doṣas*, but also that it is a separate corrupting agent. This verse, from the chapter of the Uttaratāntra on diarrhoea (*atīsāra*) and the chronic diarrhoea called *grahaṇīroga* (Uttaratāntra 40,167), runs: ‘When, in cases of diarrhoea, or even when this has ceased, the patient whose digestive fire is weak (*mandāgni*) indulges in unwholesome food, the fire becomes more corrupted; thereupon this fire corrupts (*abhidūṣayati*) the *grahaṇī*.’²⁷

This verse expresses that the digestive fire is corrupted in diarrhoea; this is a corruption caused by the *doṣas*. The already corrupted fire gets more corrupted, not by the *doṣas*, but by the intake of unwholesome food; then, in its turn, it corrupts its seat, the *grahaṇī*.

Ḍalhaṇa does not pay much attention to this verse, which makes *agni* into a separate agent, able to corrupt the *grahaṇī*. As a corrupting agent, however, it is not independent in this case and its corrupting action may, in Āyurvedic theory, be derived from the *doṣas*. This would agree with a tenet of Āyurvedic theory declaring that constituents of the body, in particular those called *dhātu*, may transmit their corruption, caused by the *doṣas*, to other constituents, in this case the *grahaṇī*. A corrupting capacity of the fire that is independent from the *doṣas* cannot be proved by the help of this verse.

Provisionally, it can be concluded that the *Suśrutasaṃhitā* contains, as does the *Carakasamhitā*, verses and passages in prose about *agni* and the *doṣas*, in particular about the connection between *agni* and *pitta*, attesting that the elab-

²⁶ *agnir annasya pācakah. ... vikriyām āpannas trividho bhavati. ... tikṣṇaḥ pittena.*

²⁷ *atisāre nivṛtte 'pi mandāgner ahitāśinaḥ
bhūyah sandūṣito vahnir grahaṇīm abhidūṣayet.*

oration of the *tridoṣa* doctrine was still a process in flux. Remnants of competing theories can be discovered, next to a tendency to encapsulate disagreeing concepts within the system that gradually succeeded in dominating medical thought.²⁸

Statements that appeared to jeopardise the *tridoṣavāda* caught the eye of the commentators and gave them much food for thought in their efforts to avert any danger to the prevailing theory. The obvious meaning of some discordant utterances was twisted until concurring with the system. Passages that were ambiguous and susceptible to various interpretations were made to conform. A conspicuous aspect of the reasonings met with is the tendency to avoid the acceptance of any bodily constituent as a factor capable, independently of the *doṣas*, of initiating physiological and, more especially, pathogenetic processes. The champion in this field is Cakrapāṇidatta, while Ḍalhaṇa is prone to give most weight to considerations relating to medical practice.

Bibliography

- BHAṬṬĀCĀRYYA, Candrakānta et al. (ed.) 1832: *Suśrutasaṃhitā – prathamakhaṇḍam – sūtra-sthānātmakam. Rāmapuraboyāliya-pravāsi-śrīHārāṇacandrakravartikavirāja-viracita-suśrutārthasandīpanabhāṣya-sametam*. Kalikātā: Satyayantra Śaka era 1832.
- BHISHAGRATNA, Kunjalal (trans. and ed.) 1963: *An English Translation of the Sushruta Samhita based on Original Sanskrit Text, with a Full and Comprehensive introduction, Additional Texts, Different Readings, Notes, Comparative Views, Index, Glossary and Plates. Vol. I. Sutra-sthāna*. Second edition. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office. The Chowkhamba Sanskrit Studies 30.
- DUTT, Uday Chand (trans.) 1883: *The Suśruta-samhitā. The Hindu System of Medicine according to Suśruta*. Calcutta: Baptist Mission Press. Bibliotheca Indica, New Series 500.
- GAUTAM, Māṇḍ'vi; UPĀDHYĀY, Om Prakāś; GAUTAM, Vinod Kumār 2005: 'Pitt evaṃ agni vivecan', *Sachitra Ayurved* 58,6: 424-427.
- GHANEKAR, Bhaskar Govind (comm.) 1952: *Sushruta Samhitā with Hindi Commentary named "Āyurveda Rahasyadīpikā"*. Volume one (*Sūtra-Nidān-Sthān*). Second edition.

²⁸ GAUTAM/UPĀDHYĀY/GAUTAM 2005, an article on the relationship between *pitta* and *agni*, concludes that they are similar (*sādharmya*) as to their actions (*karmātmak*) and treatment (*upacārātmak*), but different (*vaidharmya*) as to their own nature (*svarūp*). This makes them members of the same group (*varg*), able to cooperate.

Delhi: Meharchand Lachhmandas.

Mādhavanidāna: Mādhavanidāna by Mādhavakāra with the Commentary Madhukosha by Vijayarakshita and Shrikāṇṭhadatta and Commentary Ātānkadarpaṇa by Vāchaspati Vaidya. Edited by Vaidya Jāḍowji Tricumji Āchārya. Bombay: Nirṇaya-Sāgar Press 1920.

MEULENBELD, G. JAN *forthcoming*: 'Some Neglected Aspects of Āyurveda or The Illusion of a Consistent Theory', in: Dominik Wujastyk and Michio Yano (eds.), *Mathematics and Medicine. Proceedings of the 12th World Sanskrit Conference, Helsinki 2003* (working title).

SHARMA, Priya Vrat (ed. and trans.) 1999: *Suśruta-saṃhitā with English Translation of Text and Ḍalhana's Commentary along with Critical Notes. Vol. I (Sūtrasthāna)*. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Visvabharati. Haridas Ayurveda Series 9.

SINGHAL, G.D.; TRIPATHI, S.N.; CHATURVEDI, G.N. 1981: *Fundamental and Plastic Surgery Considerations in Ancient Indian Surgery (based on chapters 1-27 of Sūtra-sthāna of Suśruta Saṃhitā)*. Varanasi: Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University. Ancient Indian Surgery 1.

Suśrutasaṃhitā: Sushrut-Saṃhitā (Sūtra Sthān) With Bhānumatī Commentary by Chakrapāṇi Datta. ... Edited by Vaidya Jāḍavaji Trikamaji Āchārya and Pt. Nandkishor Sharmā Bhi-shagāchārya. Agra: Swāmī Lakshmī Rām Trust 1939. Shri Swāmī Lakshmī Rām Trust Series 1.

—: *The Suśrutasaṃhitā of Suśruta With the Nibandhasaṅgraha Commentary of Śrī Dalha-ṇāchārya [sic] and the Nyāyachandrikā Pañjikā of Śrī Gayadāsāchārya on Nidānasthāna.* Edited ... by Vaidya Jāḍavaji Trikamaji Āchārya and ... Nārāyaṇ Rām Āchārya. Revised third edition. Bombay: Nirṇaya Sāgar Press 1938.